

THE IMPACT OF USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN HOLIDAY DECISION MAKING BY UNDERGRADUATES OF FMSC OF USJP.

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Introduction

Background of the study

Social media has been recognized as a vogue topic in the current context mainly due to its intense usage and the influencing power on consumer behaviour. University students can be categorized into the age group who frequently use and interact more on social media. On one hand, holiday decision making being an important decision to this age group during the university vacations, it is important to understand the impact of social media on it. On the other hand, tourism being one of the major sources in developing the external affairs of a country, it is vital to discuss the topic with Sri Lanka being awarded as the best holiday destination by ‘Lonely Planet’ for the year 2019.

Research Problem

Research suggested that there is a tendency of variations toward social media as an information source in the travel industry, indicating respondents’ readiness to utilize social media for travel in near future (Ghandour & Bakalova 2014). Even Though there is a higher usage and higher influencing power by social media towards the tourism industry, the trustworthiness of social media sources can be identified as a key decision-making factor for the influencing level.

Fotis et al. 2012 revealed that content generated by users are perceived as more trustworthy when compared to official tourism websites, travel agents and mass media advertising. Hence it is considered vital to analyse the impact of social media on travel decision making.

Objectives

The study was conducted with the following objectives.

- To identify the relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision making by undergraduates of Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce (FMSC) of University of Sri Jayewardenepura (USJP) for travel purposes.
- To identify whether trustworthiness of sources affect the relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision making of undergraduates of FMSC of USJP

Methodology

A self-developed conceptual framework was used for the study where; ‘use of social media’, ‘holiday decision making’ and ‘trustworthiness of sources.’ were considered as the independent, dependent and moderating variables respectively. The hypothesis developed for the study were as follows.

H1: There is a positive relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision making.

H2: The relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision making will be negatively influenced by the trustworthiness of sources.

The research design took a quantitative approach with a self-administered online questioner targeting the undergraduates of FMSC of USJP. A sample of 125 undergraduates covering all 12 departments and all 4 years, were included using the convenient sampling method, justifying a confidence level of 95% and a confidence interval of 7%. The data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and SMART PLS software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis

The sample of 125 undergraduates comprised of 58.4% females and 41.6% males, where 48% of the total population used social media ‘very often’, 46.4% ‘often’ and only ‘5.6% ‘rarely.’ In analysing the social media platforms used by the sample, the most popular platforms were Facebook, Instagram and Blog sites having a 40.6%, 34.6% and 12% respectively.

The sample having a higher and frequent interaction with Facebook and Instagram, there is an opportunity for players in the tourism industry to use those media effectively.

Holiday decision making process analysis

Analysing the holiday decision-making process, 52% of total respondents plan trips once in every three months and 25.6% plan once in every six months. On one hand, when analysing the likeliness of changing plans after referring to social media; 12.8% of total respondents change their plans always, 48.8% mostly and 28% stand neutral.

On the other hand, 11.2% of total respondents strongly agree and 48.8% agree on the fact that they trust the information available on social media networks while 5.6% do not agree with the statement. Over 70% of respondents strongly agree and agree respectively on the fact that they trust more individual generated content compared to service provider contents.

Inferential Analysis

The reliability of the scale was tested under three measurement values (Table 1).

Table 1. Reliability of the scale

	CRONBACH'S MEASUREMENT VALUES	COMPOSITE RELIABILITY ANALYSIS VALUES	VALUES OF AVERAGE VARIANCE EXTRACTED METHOD
Trustworthiness of social media sources	1.000	1.000	1.000
Use of social media	0.445	0.781	0.642
Moderating effect	0.259	0.606	0.521
Holiday decision making	0.595	0.782	0.552

Chi-Square test indicated a statistically significant association between the frequency of social media use and holiday decision making (sig. 0.046, N=125) as the likelihood ratio below the ceiling threshold value of 0.05.

Hypothesis testing values indicated a Path coefficient of 0.36 and 0.071 with a P value of 0.00 and 0.452 for H1 and H2 respectively.

Based on the above inferential statistics, it was concluded that;

- Chi-Square analysis indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between social media use and holiday decision making. This was further reinstated by the results of the path coefficient value of 0.36 (p 0.000).
- Null hypothesis for H2 was not rejected due to the p value (sig>0.05), therefore the relationship between use of social media and holiday decision will be positively influenced by the trustworthiness of social media sources.

Conclusion

Summary

This study focused on exploring the influence of social media usage on holiday decision making of undergraduates of FMSC of USJP while evaluating the effect of trustworthiness on social media sources as a moderating variable. A quantitative

approach was taken using a self-administered questionnaire, where the data was analysed using SPSS and SMART PLS software.

Major Findings

Major findings of the study concluded that there was a statistically significant relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision making. Further, the relationship between the use of social media and holiday decision was positively influenced by the trustworthiness of social media sources. The study established that Facebook and Instagram had the highest usage rate with the majority of undergraduates preferring content generated by his/ her immediate environment but not the service suppliers' content.

Practical Implications

The findings of the study have assisted organizations in the travel industry to effectively handle social media. The practical implications of the study have contributed to the body of knowledge in the fields of social media and tourism.

Limitations

The tool used for this study only circulated through the electronic media and limitations in English were considered limitations of the study. Further, time and finance resources were identified as limitations.

Future Research

Future research could be done with other broad audiences to derive a better understanding of consumer behaviour variations that are commercially viable. Extended studies could be conducted concerning the behavioural aspect especially on spending pattern etc.

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